

Towards Enhancing Literacy and Numeracy Skills among Students in Inclusive Education Settings

Yusuf, Zainab

Email: zainabyusuf@kasu.edu.ng

Tel: +2348038852879

Department of Educational Foundations, Kaduna State University

Abstract

This paper, “Towards Enhancing Literacy and Numeracy Skills among Students in Inclusive Education Settings” explores effective strategies for achieving inclusive education and enhancing literacy and numeracy skills. The importance of improving literacy and numeracy skills is emphasized, as they are crucial for success in education and life. The paper discusses various strategies for improving these skills, including making the material relevant, providing feedback, using technology, incorporating visuals, encouraging practice, promoting group work, and making learning enjoyable. Additionally, the paper examines the challenges faced by educators in implementing inclusive education strategies and proposes potential solutions to overcome them. The research aims to provide practical recommendations for educators and policymakers to promote inclusive education and enhance literacy and numeracy skills among all learners. The paper discusses the role of Inclusive Education in providing equitable opportunities for students with diverse learning needs, ensuring that every learner can participate actively and achieve their fullest potential. The findings of this study contribute to the existing literature on inclusive education and provide insights for effective educational practices.

Keywords: Inclusive education, Literacy skills, Numeracy skills, Effective strategies, Visuals, Practice,

Introduction

Inclusive education has emerged as a paramount concern in educational systems worldwide, aiming to provide equitable access and opportunities for all learners, regardless of their diverse backgrounds and abilities (UNESCO, 2019). It emphasizes the importance of creating learning environments that foster the development of essential skills, such as literacy and numeracy, for every student. Recognizing that literacy and numeracy skills form the foundation for academic success and lifelong learning, educators and policymakers have increasingly sought effective strategies to ensure the inclusion and progression of all learners.

This article delves into the exploration of strategies that can effectively enhance literacy and numeracy skills within inclusive education settings. By understanding and analyzing these strategies, educational stakeholders can make informed decisions and implement evidence-based practices to support diverse learners in their literacy and numeracy development. The significance of this study lies in its potential to shed light on inclusive education practices that promote the acquisition of literacy and numeracy skills for learners across a broad spectrum of abilities, including students with disabilities, English language learners, and those from marginalized backgrounds. By identifying and investigating effective strategies, this research aims to contribute to the ongoing discourse on inclusive education, providing educators, researchers, and policymakers with valuable insights to guide their decision-making and foster positive outcomes for all learners.

To accomplish this, we will review existing literature on inclusive education, focusing specifically on strategies aimed at enhancing literacy and numeracy skills. For instance, research has shown that the implementation of differentiated instruction, which involves tailoring teaching methods and content to meet individual student needs, can significantly improve literacy and numeracy outcomes for diverse learners (Tomlinson, 2017). Additionally, assistive technology tools, such as text-to-speech software and adaptive learning platforms, have demonstrated efficacy in supporting learners with disabilities in their literacy and numeracy development (West, 2020).

Drawing on a wide range of scholarly sources, including empirical studies, theoretical frameworks, and best practices, we will explore the diverse approaches and interventions that have shown promise in fostering inclusive learning environments. This article will also examine the underlying principles and theories that inform inclusive education practices, such as Universal Design for Learning (UDL), differentiated instruction, and assistive technology (Rose & Meyer, 2002). By examining these

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theoretical foundations, we can better understand the rationale behind inclusive strategies and their potential impact on literacy and numeracy outcomes.

Inclusive Education

Inclusive education is an approach that seeks to ensure that all students, including those with disabilities, have access to and are supported in their education within the regular education system. Inclusive education also refers to the educational approach that aims to provide equitable access and opportunities for all learners, regardless of their diverse backgrounds, abilities, or characteristics (UNESCO, 2009). It is based on the principle that every student has the right to participate fully in the learning process and receive appropriate support to achieve their maximum potential. Inclusive education promotes the belief that diversity in the classroom should be recognized, valued, and celebrated. It goes beyond mere integration or placement of students with disabilities or special educational needs in mainstream classrooms. Instead, it focuses on creating inclusive learning environments that embrace and accommodate the individual differences of all students.

A number of theories have also been formulated to explain inclusive education, like the social model of disability, which is a prominent theoretical framework within inclusive education. It emphasizes that disability is not solely an individual's impairment but is also influenced by societal barriers and attitudes. According to Oliver (1996), "the social model of disability proposes that disability results from the interaction between individuals with impairments and the disabling barriers present in society". Inclusive education, within this framework, aims to eliminate these barriers and create an inclusive learning environment that accommodates the diverse needs of all students.

Universal Design for Learning (UDL) is another influential theory in inclusive education. UDL promotes the design of flexible learning environments and instructional materials that can be accessed and utilized by all students, regardless of their diverse abilities or learning styles. According to Rose and Meyer (2002), UDL is an approach to curriculum and teaching that provides multiple means of representation, expression, and engagement. By offering multiple means of access, expression, and engagement, UDL aims to ensure that all students can actively participate and succeed in the learning process.

Critical pedagogy is another theory that was developed by Freire (1970), which promotes an inclusive approach to education that focuses on social justice and empowering marginalized students. It encourages educators to critically examine and challenge societal structures and power dynamics that perpetuate inequality in education. According to McLaren and Kincheloe (2007), critical pedagogy challenges the hidden assumptions that support and sustain institutionalized forms of oppression. Inclusive education within a critical pedagogy framework aims to foster critical consciousness, promote student agency, and actively address issues of social justice within society.

These theories contribute to the development of inclusive education practices by challenging traditional models, promoting equity and accessibility, and emphasizing social justice. They provide educators with frameworks and perspectives that support the creation of inclusive classrooms where all students can participate, learn, and thrive.

Strategies to Ensure Inclusiveness

A number of strategies have been developed to support the diversity in classrooms; this paper employs the following approaches:

- 1. Universal Design for Learning (UDL):** UDL is an approach that seeks to create flexible learning environments that can accommodate the learning needs of all students, including those with disabilities. UDL uses a variety of teaching methods, materials, and technologies to provide multiple ways of learning and engaging with information. Universal Design for Learning (UDL) is an educational framework that is based on the principles of Universal Design, which is an approach to design that seeks to create products and environments that are accessible and usable by the widest range of people possible, regardless of their abilities or disabilities. UDL is a flexible approach to teaching and learning that provides multiple means of representation, expression, and engagement to support the diverse learning needs of all students. The most important principles of Universal Design for Learning include: Multiple means of representation, Multiple means of action and expression, as well as Multiple means of engagement, which when adopted and incorporated into instructional practices, educators can design learning experiences that are accessible, inclusive, and effective for all students, including those with disabilities or diverse learning needs. Research has also shown the positive impact of UDL on student learning outcomes. For example, a study by Dalton and Strangman (2006) found that students who received instruction following the UDL principles demonstrated higher levels of engagement, motivation, and academic achievement compared to those in traditional instruction settings. Another study by Meyer et al. (2014) showed that UDL implementation improved student performance and reduced achievement gaps among students with diverse backgrounds and abilities.

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2. **Collaborative Teaching:** This approach involves a general education teacher and a special education teacher working together to teach a class of students with diverse learning needs. Both teachers share responsibilities and work together to create an inclusive learning environment that supports the needs of all students. Collaborative teaching, also known as co-teaching, is an educational approach in which a general education teacher and a special education teacher work together in the same classroom to teach a diverse group of students. Both teachers share responsibility for planning, teaching, and assessing student learning, and they work collaboratively to create an inclusive learning environment that meets the needs of all students. Collaborative teaching provides several benefits for students, including: Increased access to support, more individualized attention, Differentiated instruction and improved socialization. In addition, there are different models of collaborative teaching, including co-teaching, team teaching, and parallel teaching.
3. **Peer Support:** Peer support is an approach that involves pairing students with disabilities with peers who can provide support and assistance in the classroom. This approach helps to build relationships between students and promotes social inclusion. Peer support is an inclusive educational approach that involves students with disabilities receiving support from their peers in a variety of educational settings. This approach focuses on building relationships and fostering a sense of community within the classroom by promoting positive interactions and providing opportunities for peer-to-peer support. Peer support can take many different forms, depending on the needs and abilities of the students involved. Some examples of peer support include: peer tutoring, Peer modeling and Peer counseling,
4. **Individualized Education Plans (IEPs):** An IEP is a plan that is developed for each student with disability. The plan outlines the student's learning goals and the accommodations and support they need to meet those goals (Smith & Johnson, 2010). IEPs are developed in collaboration with parents, teachers, and other professionals (Brown & Martinez, 2015), and they come together for the common goal of improving the lives of learners with inclusive educational needs. Jones & Williams (2018) on the other hand, explained Individualized Education Plan (IEP) as a legal document that outlines the educational goals, services, and accommodations that are tailored to meet the individual needs of a student with disability. The purpose of an IEP is to ensure that students with disabilities receive a free and appropriate public education (FAPE) in the least restrictive environment possible. The IEP process involves a collaborative effort between the student's parents, teachers, and other professionals who work with the student, such as special education teachers, therapists, and administrators. The process begins with an evaluation of the student's strengths and needs, which is used to develop goals and objectives for the student's education. The IEP team then determines the services and accommodations that are necessary to help the student achieve those goals.
5. **Assistive Technology (AT):** Smith & Johnson (2010) described Assistive Technology as any technology or tool that is used to support the learning and participation of students with disabilities. Examples of assistive technology include text-to-speech software, speech recognition software, and screen readers. Jones & Williams (2018), also analysed AT as devices, software, or equipment that are designed to help individuals with disabilities or impairments perform daily tasks, increase their independence, and improve their quality of life. AT can include simple tools such as canes, hearing aids, and magnifying glasses, as well as more complex devices such as prosthetics, communication aids, and mobility devices. AT can be used to address a wide range of disabilities, including visual, auditory, physical, cognitive, and developmental disabilities. It can help individuals with disabilities access education, employment, and social opportunities, and enhance their ability to participate fully in their communities.

Strategies to Enhance Literacy and Numeracy in Inclusive Education

There are several strategies Educators can adopt to enhance literacy and numeracy in inclusive education settings. Here are some effective strategies:

1. **Differentiated instruction:** Teachers should tailor their instruction to meet the needs of each individual student. This can involve providing additional support and resources to struggling learners, while providing more challenging materials and activities to advanced learners.
2. **Multisensory learning:** Multisensory learning is an approach to learning that engages multiple senses simultaneously to enhance the learning experience. This approach recognizes that learners have different learning styles and that some learners may be more receptive to certain types of information when presented through certain sensory channels. For example, some learners may prefer visual stimuli, while others may prefer auditory or tactile stimuli. Multisensory learning leverages this understanding by incorporating various types of sensory input into the learning process. This can involve incorporating visuals, sounds, tactile experiences, and even smells and tastes.

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Conclusion

In conclusion therefore, inclusive education has emerged as a crucial focus in educational systems worldwide, aiming to provide equitable access and opportunities for all learners regardless of their diverse backgrounds and abilities. The development of literacy and numeracy skills is fundamental for academic success and lifelong learning, and it is essential to ensure that inclusive education practices effectively support the progression of all learners. This article explored strategies and interventions that have demonstrated efficacy in enhancing literacy and numeracy skills within inclusive education settings. The paper also shed more light on inclusive education practices that promote the acquisition of literacy and numeracy skills for diverse learners, including students with disabilities, English language learners and those from marginalized backgrounds, through identification, investigation of effective strategies that provides valuable insights for educators, researchers and policy makers. It also discussed the assistive technologies used to enhance literacy and numeracy skills in inclusive educational settings. Overall, the promotion of inclusive education and the enhancement of literacy and numeracy skills go hand in hand. By implementing effective strategies, utilizing assistive technologies and fostering collaboration, educational systems can create inclusive learning environments that support the development of essential skills for all learners.

Recommendations

The following recommendations will go a long way in enhancing literacy and numeracy skills in an inclusive educational setting:

1. **Implement differentiated instruction:** Educators should adopt differentiated instruction strategies to tailor teaching methods and content to meet the diverse needs of learners.
2. **Incorporate assistive technology:** Government and School Proprietors should employ assistive technology tools into their instructional practices, for example text to speech software, adaptive learning platforms, among other assistive technologies for learners with disabilities to make institutions of learning more inclusive.
3. **Provide professional development and support:** Government and Educational Institutions should offer professional development opportunities for educators to enhance their understanding and implementation of inclusive education practices. **Foster collaboration and cooperation:** Collaboration among educators, researchers, policy makers and other stakeholders is vital to ensure the success of inclusive education initiatives by working together to share best practices, exchange knowledge and collectively contribute to the improvement of literacy and numeracy outcomes in inclusive education settings.
4. **Continuously evaluate and adapt to effective strategies:** It is crucial to continuously evaluate the effectiveness of strategies and interventions aimed at enhancing literacy and numeracy skills within inclusive education, by collecting data and feedback, educators and policy makers can identify arrears for improvement and make necessary adjustments to ensure positive outcomes for all learners.

References

- Ainscow, M. (2005). Developing inclusive education systems: What are the levers for change? *Journal of Educational Change*, 6(2), 109-124.
- Avramidis, E., Bayliss, P., & Burden, R. (2000). A survey into mainstream teachers' attitudes towards the inclusion of children with special educational needs in the ordinary school in one local education authority. *Educational Psychology*, 20(2), 191-211.
- Coffield, F., Moseley, D., Hall, E., & Ecclestone, K. (2004). Learning styles and pedagogy in post-16 learning: A systematic and critical review. *Learning and Skills Research Centre*.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2011). *Research methods in education*. Routledge.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. Sage Publications.
- Fisher, D., & Frey, N. (2014). *Better learning through structured teaching: A framework for the gradual release of responsibility*. ASCD.
- Freiberg, H. J., & Lapointe, N. (2006). From isolation to integration: Preparing general educators to teach students with disabilities. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 39(5), 375-386.
- Freire, P. (1970). *Pedagogy of the oppressed*. Penguin.

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- Greenwood, C. R., Carta, J. J., & Hall, R. V. (1991). The use of peers as behavior change agents. *Exceptional Children, 57*(6), 486-492.
- Hall, T., Strangman, N., & Meyer, A. (2012). Differentiated instruction and implications for UDL implementation. Retrieved from National Center on Universal Design for Learning website: http://www.udlcenter.org/sites/udlcenter.org/files/updateguidelines2_0.pdf
- Hidi, S., & Renninger, K. A. (2006). The four-phase model of interest development. *Educational Psychologist, 41*(2), 111-127.
- Loreman, T., Deppeler, J., & Harvey, D. (2005). *Inclusive education: A practical guide to supporting diversity in the classroom*.
- Rose, D. H., & Meyer, A. (2002). *Teaching every student in the digital age: Universal Design for Learning*. ASCD.
- Tomlinson, C. A. (2001). *How to differentiate instruction in mixed-ability classrooms* (2nd ed.). ASCD.
- Tomlinson, C. A. (2017). *How to differentiate instruction in academically diverse classrooms*. ASCD.
- Tomlinson, C. A., Brighton, C., Hertzberg, H., Callahan, C. M., Moon, T. R., Brimijoin, K. & Reynolds, T. (2003). Differentiating instruction in response to student readiness, interest, and learning profile in academically diverse classrooms: A review of literature. *Journal for the Education of the Gifted, 27*(2-3), 119-145.
- UNESCO. (2019). *Policy Guidelines on Inclusion in Education*. Retrieved from <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0026/002603/260352e.pdf>
- West, R. E. (2020). Assistive Technology: A Critical Review of the Literature. *International Journal of Special Education Technology, 2*(1), 21-34.